

Structure of the model values of the individual physical education of schoolchildren of different age groups

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The proposed article presents the results of an empirical study, on the basis of which models of individual physical culture of boys and girls are developed.

Purpose: *identification of factors that encourage students to engage in physical exercise and the development of a model of value orientations of the individual physical culture of boys and girls in different age periods.*

Material & Methods: *research was carried out with a contingent of schoolchildren of grades 5–11. The total number of respondents was 628 people (boys – 282; girls – 346), of which 126 respondents (97 boys and 29 girls) are engaged in a certain sport. To solve the problems of our study, at the first stage a survey was conducted of respondents "Determining the motives and interests of schoolchildren in the field of physical culture and sports".*

Results: *according to the results of the survey of respondents we were first created models of value orientations of individual physical culture of boys and girls of different age groups.*

Conclusion: *It was found that the representation of schoolchildren who are not involved in sports about the quality, characterizing a physically cultured person, primarily concerns sports activities. More harmoniously characterize the priority qualities of the individual physical education of the person of a young man who play sports.*

Keywords: *students, boys, girls, physical education, values, individual physical culture.*

Introduction

The lifestyle of modern schoolchildren is characterized by a high level of static, sensory and informational load and at the same time – a low level of general motor activity [6]. Physical education, as an academic discipline in educational institutions, aims to solve not only educational, recreational and educational tasks, but also to form a valuable attitude to health and a healthy lifestyle, nurturing interest and need for physical activity [3]. Unfortunately, today physical culture is losing its value for young people. Children and teenagers prefer to virtual space and social networking. Despite the fact that a school is an educational institution, it directs its activity towards the harmonious development of children, according to the data of scientists, T. Yu. Krutsevich [4], A. G. Sukhareva [8] and other scientists [9–11], there is a significant decrease in the motor activity of schoolchildren, as a result of which their physical condition and morbidity level decreases. According to I. A. Kogut, V. V. Romanenko, G. E. Motylyanskaya, interest in physical education and sports is gradually declining: a long stay at a desk, a rest – mainly at a computer or watching TV. This all limits the motor activity of schoolchildren, which leads to significant disruptions in the functioning of their body [1; 2]. The need to change the attitude of students to physical education is one of the most important tasks in the educational process. It is for this psychological parameter that one can assess how and how much physical education corresponds to the value standards and attitudes of schoolchildren, their condition, needs, interests and motives [5]. This requires the search for scientifically grounded theoretical propositions about the possibility of influencing this process in the course of educational and educational activities, determining the rel-

evance of our chosen research topic. Also in the available literature, we did not find scientific papers that studied the age and sex differences of students in the formation of models of individual physical culture, and justifies the relevance of our scientific research.

Purpose of the study:

- study of the peculiarities of representations of schoolchildren of different age groups on the motivational priorities and value orientations of the individual physical culture of young men and women who are engaged in and not in sports;
- development of a model of value orientations of individual physical education of boys and girls in different age periods.

Material and Methods of the research

Research methods – analysis of scientific and methodological literature, respondent questioning, methods of mathematical statistics.

The study was carried out with a contingent of schoolchildren of 5–11 grades with an increase in the representativeness of the sample. The total number of respondents was 628 people (boys – 282; girls – 346). The results of the study stratified according to the age periods of the physiological development of children and biological sex. The reliability of differences between individual results is calculated at the level of reliability $p < 0,05$ to $p < 0,1$, which indicates the possibility of taking them into account when developing practical recommendations for physical culture teachers, as well as for further inter-

pretations.

To find out the motivation of schoolchildren in the field of physical education and further determination of the ways of its formation, it is necessary to identify their motives and actions, which they are guided by their actions and desires. Therefore, knowing the attitude of students to the subject "Physical Culture", motives, interests and determining the place occupied by physical culture and sports in the life of schoolchildren, it is possible to influence their motivation to physical self-improvement and to some extent improve the process of physical education at school. To solve the problems of our research, at the first stage, a survey was conducted of respondents "Determining the motives and interests of schoolchildren in the field of physical culture and sports". The survey was conducted by a group method, which made it possible to get a fairly high rate of return of high-quality completed questionnaires – up to 95%. This provision indicates a high interest of students and a high level of reliability and reliability of the empirical data. Boys and girls of different ages took part in this survey, regardless of the degree of activity and their participation in various forms of physical culture and sports activities.

Results of the research

According to the results of the survey, it has been established that young men are more likely to choose power sports: taekwondo, wrestling and football. From the 5th to the 11th classes, for various reasons, the number of young people engaged in sports activities are significantly reduced (Fig. 1). Of the 98% of the guys who are engaged in physical education and sports activities in the 5th class, 26,6% of the eight students remained. In early adolescence (15–17 years old) certain relations with the outside world already consist. School age is sensitive for the formation of value orientations. The needs of high school students for self-development, self-improvement and self-realization become urgent, which is an indicator of personal maturity and at the same time a condition for its achievement. Therefore, starting or continuing to play sports at a given age, schoolchildren become more motivated and purposeful. A young man of 15–17 years old is already aware of the purpose of his actions and relates them to the motives of physical self-improvement. Starting playing sports at a given age, young men direct their activities not to a high athletic result, but to a greater degree to the improvement of the body and body shape.

Figure 1. Number of students in grades 5–11 who are engaged in sports and recreational activities (boys), %

After the ranking of the interests of girls in grades 5–11 to sports, it was found that 75% of fifth graders are engaged in sports and recreational activities after hours (Figure 2). They chose the following sports: swimming, volleyball, types of fitness. But 25% of girls who are not involved in sports – 17% want to attend sports clubs. In most cases, this is a type of fitness occupation. In the 6th grade, the percentage of schoolchildren engaged in sporting activities decreased to 70,5%, and in the 7th grade to 33,3%. So, we can observe that from the 5th to the 7th grade girls also revealed some decrease in the interest in sports, as in the guys of this age. Further, we note the positive dynamics: from the 8th to the eleventh grades the percentage of schoolgirls who are engaged in physical culture and sports activities increases from 42% to 53%. Despite the shown age-related positive dynamics in school and sports activities of schoolchildren, the percentage of those who are indifferent to physical activity remained quite substantial. Also with age there is a gradual decrease in the number of schoolchildren who regularly play sports.

Figure 2. Number of students in grades 5–11 who are engaged in sports and recreational activities (girls), %

Continuing our research in determining the relationship of young people to physical activity and sport, exploring their motivations, interests and hobbies in the sphere of physical culture, we analyzed the answers to the following question: "What motivates you to exercise?" (Table 1). The most common among children aged 11–12 years old (grades 5–6) were the answers "give parents advice" and "give advice to a physical education teacher". Pupils of the 7th and 8th grades put the motive of the impulses to exercise "programs on TV" also in the first place. The second place was taken by the answer – "friends advised". For high school students, the first place according to the rating is the answer: "knowledge about the benefits of exercise". That is, a conscious choice of such an answer among young men who are not involved in sports may indicate a sufficient level of external information about the effect of exercise on the general level of physical fitness and physical health of a person. And if they still have not been involved in sports, there is hope that they have sufficiently weighty motivation to engage in physical culture and recreation activities. In the girls of the 5th and 6th grades of the answer: "programs on TV" and "gave advice to a teacher of physical culture" occupy the first positions. That is, we see a slight difference in the answers of boys and girls, about who has more influence on the decision-making, and whether this decision is independent. Thus, among 11–12 year olds, the advice and examples of parents and teachers see a significant role in making this or that decision. But girls at this age are already more independent in making decisions, the emotional

component begins to prevail in them. With age, boys and girls have changed the motivation. Already in the 10th and 11th grades, the girls put the answer "knowledge about the benefits of exercise" in the first place, the answer to the "broadcast on TV" remained in the second place. In young men, the first place was taken by the answer "give advice to friends." The second is "knowledge of the benefits of exercise." Physical education and sports significantly affect the system of values, interests and views of adolescents. And the answer of the respondents "knowledge about the benefits of exercise" indicates the consciousness of the choice of adolescents. Comparing the answers of schoolchildren involved in sports, one can determine that their first priority is the motive of knowledge about the benefits of physical culture and sports. At the young men on the second and third places – "to improve the physical form". Analyzing the motives for conducting physical exercises, we found the difference in respondents' answers by age and sex, and comparing the impulses during physical exercises, we found no significant difference between the answers of boys and girls. So, it has been established that the influence of parents on the decision-making of adolescents at the age of 16–17 decreases, but the authority of other people and their opinion become more influential. Thus, the motivation of adolescents in sports and recreational activities, regardless of whether they are systematically involved in sports or not, have a significant influence on the opinions of parents, friends and on television and the Internet. In older teens and adolescents, a more conscious influence of information that may become a motivated stimulus to exercise.

In order to clarify the value qualities in the imagination of schoolchildren personify physical culture, we raised the question: "Who do you consider a physically cultured person? Taking into account the answers of schoolchildren to this question and the qualitative characteristics of their individual physical culture, we have developed models of value orientations of individual physical culture of boys and girls in different age periods (Figure 3, 4). According to the rating, the majority of respondents 11–13 years old put the answer to the first place: "the one who plays sports". The priority qualities of the guys attributed "the one who owns physical skills in various sports" and "the one who achieved and maintains his level of physical

health at a high level". The girls of this age have somewhat different priorities: "the one who has achieved and maintains his level of physical health at a high level" and "the one who has achieved the harmony of physical and spiritual development. Boys of 14–15 years old as priorities characterizing a physically cultured person are also considered to be the person involved in sports (1st place) and maintaining a healthy lifestyle (HLS) (2nd place). The third place is occupied by the one who has achieved and maintains his level of physical health at a high level. Girls at this age gave preference to those who play sports (1st place). Further, according to the rating, appeared those who support a healthy lifestyle (2nd place). In the 11th grade, the girls placed the answer in the first place in the definition of a physico-cultural person: "the one who adheres to a healthy lifestyle"; then, according to the rating, the answer is "the one who achieved the harmony of physical and spiritual development" and "the one who supports your level of physical health at a high level". Attention is drawn to the fact that "regular exercise by yourself" according to the rating is in the last places both in boys and girls (Figure 3).

More harmoniously characterize the priority qualities of the individual physical culture of a young man's person who play sports. "Regular exercise by yourself" in them, by rating, is one of the priorities. The representation of schoolchildren who are not involved in sports, about the quality, characterizing a physically cultured person, primarily concerns sports activities. On the 2nd place – knowledge about the effect of exercise on the human body, on the 3rd – compliance with healthy lifestyles. The fourth place is given to the harmony of the physical and spiritual development of a person, on the fifth – possession of a wide range of motor skills and skills, the sixth place is given to the ability to make an individual training program and only then (seventh place) the regularity of independent lessons is taken into account.

Unfortunately, but the main goal of physical education is to achieve a high level of physical health and maintain it for a long period of time, they remain at one of the last places, which indicates the lack of formation of the essence of the concepts of "physical culture" and "sports" in both schoolchildren of both articles.

Table 1
Factors that motivate students to exercise (%)

Grade	Gender	Teacher of physical education gave advice	Parents give advice	Friends give advice	Answer choices				
					TV shows	Knowledge of the benefits of exercise	Attendance of competitions	Publications in newspapers, magazines	Other
5	b	14,3	71,4	19,0	47,6	14,3	14,3	0,0	0,0
	g	11,3	39,6	20,8	50,9	15,1	0,0	28,3	0,0
6	b	34,0	60,0	18,0	30,0	4,0	18,0	14,0	0,0
	g	5,6	24,1	29,6	64,8	18,5	35,2	40,7	0,0
7	b	26,5	14,7	52,9	52,9	5,9	20,6	20,6	0,0
	g	7,7	7,7	41,0	82,1	0,0	7,7	33,3	0,0
8	b	23,6	23,6	32,7	32,7	9,1	9,1	5,5	9,1
	g	14,8	18,5	27,8	61,1	14,8	9,3	38,9	9,3
9	b	14,4	24,4	31,1	53,3	7,8	14,4	2,2	14,4
	g	12,7	20,0	23,6	47,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	20,0
10	b	8,3	8,3	8,3	25,0	58,3	0,0	0,0	16,7
	g	13,3	26,7	20,0	53,3	33,3	6,7	0,0	13,3
11	b	7,3	21,9	21,9	43,9	21,9	12,2	0,0	12,2
	g	7,7	20,0	20,0	30,7	35,4	6,1	3,1	9,2

Figure 3. Models of value orientations of individual physical culture of boys and girls in different age groups

Conclusions / Discussion

Today, the authors of most modern publications believe that physical education should be directed to the formation (education) of a person not only certain physical qualities, but also deep knowledge about his body, a means of purposeful impact on the physical condition, preservation and strengthening of health, and moreover the formation of relevant interests, needs, value orientations and real behavior (lifestyle), that is, the "physical culture of the individual" [7, pp. 425]. We fully agree with the opinion of A. A. Tomenko, substantiated and developed a conceptual model of non-special physical education for students. Highlighting its theoretical aspects, the scientist noted the need to distinguish between the specific functions of non-special physical education education and general cultural, based on interrelations with other spheres of life activity [9].

Thus, according to the results of the survey of respondents, we for the first time created models of value orientations of the individual physical culture of boys and girls of different age groups. It was found that the representation of schoolchildren who are not involved in sports about the quality, characterizing a physically cultured person, primarily concerns sports activities. More harmoniously characterize the priority quali-

ties of the individual physical education of the person who play sports. But in general, we can state the fact of insufficient formation of the essence of the concepts "physical culture" and "sport" among schoolchildren of both sexes. At the same time, the study of the formation of the values of individual physical education of schoolchildren allows us to conclude that the general level of non-special physical education that they were supposed to receive in a secondary school when studying the school subject "physical culture" is low. Their representation in this field is based primarily on practical experience and, to a lesser extent, on theoretical knowledge. The results obtained give us the right to argue about the existence of certain differences in both the created models of individual physical culture of boys and girls, and in the motivational priorities of conducting physical activity classes. Therefore, we can admit the idea that in order to form a certain strategy of attracting young people to systematic physical education, studying the interests, motives, value orientations in the field of physical culture, their relation to physical activity, it is impossible to focus only on one of the indicators of biological or psychosocial systems, it is necessary to take into account not only physiological and morpho-functional features of schoolchildren, but also the whole complex of biosocial personality traits, introducing gender and follow in the physical education. Taking into account the foregoing, we consider it expedient to fur-

Figure 4. Models of value orientations of the individual physical culture of boys and girls who are engaged in sports

ther develop the concept of a gender approach in education, which will promote the development of individual abilities of schoolchildren of different sexes, overcoming of polo-role stereotypes and more effective formation of their values of physical culture.

Prospects for further research. The next stage of our scientific research will be devoted to identifying the relationship between the psychological gender of the respondents and their models of individual physical culture.

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